

ISic0320

Fragments of a mosaic

Language

Latin

Type

calendar (?)

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2017.07.01

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491526

TM 491527

TM 491528

TM 491529

EDR 141138

EDR 141139

EDR 141140

EDR 141141

EDCS 21900358

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7036 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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